
CROPPING PATTERN IN BAYANA OF BHARATPUR DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

The seed spices occupy an important position in earning of foreign exchange. A large number of spices are grown in India. During 2019-20, production of seed spices in India's was 9.4 million metric tons respectively. Present study is conducted during the year 2020-21. The study was primarily based on primary data, the size of holding varied from farmer to farmer. Hence, a purposive non-random sampling was adopted for the present study. Total numbers of sample farms 46 from different categories were selected purposively from **Veerampura (Bayana)** villages of **Bharatpur** District of **Rajasthan**. The study indicated that under diversified agro-climatic conditions of fennel have given encouraging results over farmers practice and have potential to perform well in flood prone eastern plain zone 3B of Rajasthan. In this research paper an attempt has been made to study the cropping pattern on Fennel growing farms. This research paper deals with the land utilization pattern in the study area. The use of improved production technologies with timely systematic management would increase productivity of fennel. This will substantially increase the income as well as the livelihood of the farming community who are mainly associated with this crop. This study is conducted for analyze the cropping pattern on fennel growing farms in study area.

Keywords: Spices, Fennel Crop, Cropping Pattern, Land Utilization Pattern.

I. INTRODUCTION

India has been known from time immemorial times as the "land of spices". India had a virtual dominance in the international spices trade. Agriculture plays a vital role in the Indian economy. Agriculture sector employ 58.2 per cent of the total workforce. This sector supplies bulk of raw materials required by the non-agricultural sectors and raw material for a large section of industry. Horticulture, being one of the important sectors of Indian agriculture, plays an important role in the economy of the country. There are several horticulture crops suitable for almost all the agro-climatic zones of the country. As per 2020, agriculture employed more than 50% of the Indian work force and contributed 19.9% to country's GDP. In 2019 agriculture and allied sectors like animal husbandry, forestry and fisheries accounted for 15.4% of the GDP (gross domestic product) with about 41.49% of the workforce in 2020. Currently horticulture contributes 30.04 per cent of agricultural GDP. Country has emerged as the world's largest producer of mango, banana, coconut cashew and spices.

India still continues to be the largest producer, consumer and exporter of spices in the world. It produced 5.80 million tonnes of spices on an area of 3.10 million hectares. India commands leading position in world spices trade with 48 per cent (502750 tonnes) share in volume and 43 per cent (5560.5 crores) in value. The seed spices export from India has registered an all time high both in term of quantity (142300 tonnes) and value (985.58 crores). The major markets for different seed spices are USA, UAE, UK and South Africa (Annual Report 2012-13, National Research Centre on Seed Spices, Ajmer). Thus, spices occupy an important position in earning of foreign exchange. A large number of spices are grown in India. Out of the 109 spices listed by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), India produces as many as 63 owing to its varied agro climatic regions. Almost all the States and Union territories (UTs) of the country grow one or the other spices. It is a source livelihood and employment for large number of people in the country, both for rural population, who grow them, and the urban population, who process and trade in them. Out of the total 63 spices grown in India, 20 are classified as seed spices with 36 per cent share in area and 17 per cent share in production of total

spice in India. Main seed spices of India are coriander, cumin, fennel, fenugreek, dill, ajwain, celery, anise nigella and caraway. Seed spice crops are extensively cultivated in the arid and semi arid region of India during rabi season covering an area of 12.20 lakh hectare with production of 10.58 lakh tones annually. Global fennel production data showing each of the countries producing this commodity is not available. Based on the available information, India is believed to be the world’s largest fennel producing country. The area under fennel production in India is estimated at 90,000 hectares, yielding 149,000 tons in 2017-18 (NHB, 2017).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study is based on primary as well as secondary data. The study information were collected through survey method by personal interview of the sample farmers with the help of pretested schedule. The study confined to the Bayana Block of Bharatpur District of Rajasthan. At the first stage of sampling one village Veerampura was selected purposively for the purpose of study. At the second and final stage of selection of the list of cultivators was taken from (Khasara-Khatoni record) of tehsil along with their size of holding. Then Village Development Officer was consulted to know the extent of area under fennel cultivation during the year 2020-21. All the farmers in the village grow high yielding varieties of fennel. The number of cases falling in the different farm size groups came to 26 in marginal, 24 in small and 22 in medium and 20 in large farm size groups. About 50 percent cases were selected. Thus the final sample comprises of 13 in marginal, 12 in small, 11 in medium and 10 in large farm size groups.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A good place to being with overall organization or plan of the farm is with the cropping system. In cropping program farmer decides that how the limited available resources, agro-climatic conditions and in a scientific manner. In good speaking cropping pattern refers the area of crops and crop combination which the cultivators follow within specific period of time. The type of crops grown on a particular farm play important role in its costs and income position. Mainly the soil type, size of holding, source of irrigation, level of investment and availability of resources influence cropping pattern within a homogenous agro-climate area. It provides an idea regarding the intensity with which the farmers are using their land and other resources. The cropping pattern is a most important aspect of farm practices as the farm economy of the cultivators directly affected by it.

Table – 1: Cropping pattern on different farm size groups (in hect.)

Crop	Farm size groups									
	Marginal		Small		Medium		Large		Overall	
	Area	%	Area	%	Area	%	Area	%	Area	%
Bajra / Jowar	0.60	41.68	1.28	48.12	2.70	48.13	4.15	45.55	2.05	46.49
Other	0.03	2.08	0.03	1.12	0.03	0.53	0.25	2.75	0.09	2.04
Total Kharif	0.63	43.75	1.31	49.24	2.73	48.66	4.40	48.30	2.14	48.53
Fennal	0.21	14.58	0.33	12.41	0.48	8.56	0.53	5.82	0.38	8.62
Wheat/ Mustard	0.45	31.25	0.95	35.71	2.15	38.26	3.88	42.59	1.73	39.22
Other	0.10	6.94	0.03	0.03	1.12	0	0	0	0.01	0.23
Total Rabi	0.76	52.77	1.31	49.24	2.63	46.88	4.41	48.40	2.12	48.07
Total Zaid	0.05	3.47	0.04	1.50	0.25	4.46	0.30	3.29	0.15	3.40
Cropped Area	1.44	100%	2.66	100%	5.61	100%	9.11	100%	4.41	100%

Table 1 represent per farm area under various crop grown in the study area. The overall average cropped area per farm was 9.96 hac. Being 1.44, 2.66, 5.61 and 9.11 hectares on marginal, small, medium and large farms respectively. Out of total cropped area, kharif and rabi both season crops occupied the about 48.53 and 48.07

percent respectively, while only about 3.40 percent of cropped area was occupied by zaid crops. Fennel crop are the main spices crop of respective seasons and occupied about 8.62 percent of the total cropped area respectively. Besides these crops bajra, jawar and wheat, mustard were the other important crops of kharif and Rabi season.

IV. CONCLUSION

It is clear from the table- 1 that bajra and jowar crop are major gainer whereas other kharif season crops have lost its share in cropping pattern. Wheat and mustard crops emerged as major gainer in rabi season. In fact, development of irrigation resulted into more acreage under fennel. This increase can be attributed to decline in the sown area of other rabi season crops.

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